

EXPRESSION OF THE EPITHET IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: The article analyzes the features of the functional styles of English and Uzbek languages, the difficulty of understanding texts in different styles.

Key words: text, text reading, functional styles.

Абстрактный: В статье анализируются особенности функциональных стилей английского и узбекского языка, определение сложности восприятия текстов разных стилей.

Ключевые слова: текст, чтение текста, функциональные стили.

A text is a set of sentences organized in a certain way with a communicative task. The main features of the text: semantic and communicative unity; consists of structural integrity. Any language has systems known as speech styles or functional styles. Styles are the richness and diversity of any language. Learning the basic techniques in English and Uzbek will seriously enrich your understanding of the language and help you learn it. In the process of language learning, reading texts belongs to various functional styles: conversational, artistic, scientific, journalistic (popular), official styles.

Functional language styles are a system of interrelated languages that serve a specific purpose of communication. A functional style serves as a product of an absolute task organized by the sender of the message. Functional styles are often found in the literary part of the language. [1]. Although all functional styles are in a unique way, various features are interrelated as a system, despite the fact that language is the main feature of a group of communication tools, it will not be enough to determine the requested functional style. Each functional style depends on a stable system at the stage of development of the literary language, but it sometimes changes frequently as it passes from one period to the next. Therefore, the functional styles of the language are considered a historical series (category). Examples are enough to prove this concept. Consequently, the poetry (artistic) style of the functional style began to function as an independent style in the second half of the 16th

century; newspaper style is separated from journalistic style; Like other functional styles, the style of speaking has undergone significant changes.

The development of each style is predetermined by changes in the norms of the standard English and Uzbek languages. Changes in social conditions, scientific progress, and the development of cultural life have a great impact on this. The traditionally distinguished functional styles — scientific (popular science), formal, journalistic (popular), colloquial, artistic — are language subsystems, each of which is unique at five main levels: phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic and text structure features.

Functional styles are distinguished by the possibility or not of the use of certain elements and structures, as well as their communication systems. For example, phonetic tools are important for the style of speaking: compliance with pronunciation standards, wide use of intonation; for the scientific method - syntactic: clear syntactic structure, direct order of words, wide use of words, wide use of various specific and specific systems, at the text level : logical, clear presentation structure (newspaper or magazine article). The text of the official style is characterized by the presence of special terms (commercial, legal, etc.), stamps, specialized foreign expressions, abbreviations, mixed words, absence of figurative means at the lexical level; at the syntactic level - complex structures are formed by the wide use of sentences in the passive tense of the verb.

Functional styles are found in written and spoken form. The speech style is characterized by the presence of short sentences, two-syllable words, phonetic and syntactic abbreviations. Artistic style combines three sub-styles: poetic style of language, emotional (artistic) prose style and dramatic style. There are common characteristics for each of these sub-styles and for individual sub-styles as well. Artistic texts also have a number of difficulties, because they combine logical-intellectual information with figurative-emotional information.

Reading popular style texts can be difficult. It should be noted that the peculiarity of this style is that some of the texts are scientific, and some are close to texts of other styles. Texts on journalism are distinguished by their coverage of political vocabulary, phraseological units, abbreviations, realisms, newspaper articles, expressions and various

topics. Newspaper and magazine publications have a variety of headlines, including advertising and emotionally appealing ones. Two types of popular style are found in oral speech: speech style and the text of radio and television programs, as well as newspaper style in written speech. The written forms of the popular style are essays (philosophical, literary, moral) and journalistic articles (political, social, economic, etc.). The general purpose of the journalistic style is to influence public opinion, to convince the reader or listener that the opinion given by the author is the only true one, and to encourage him to accept the expressed opinion. Popular style is characterized by a clear and logical syntactic structure, extensive use of connectives, and the division of the text into parts. Oratorical style is a verbal form of journalistic style. Direct communication with listeners allows using syntactic, lexical and phonetic features of written and spoken speech. Distinctive features of this method are direct appeal to the people; sometimes - it is characterized by the use of words related to the style of speech. The stylistic means involved in the speech style are determined by the communicative situation. The speaker often uses analogies and metaphors, but usually uses traditional methods because individual stylistic devices can be difficult to perceive.

Texts in the scientific style are aimed at promoting the achievements of science and technology to a wide readership. Usually, the material is presented in an interesting and convenient way, using a certain amount of numerical data, formulas, diagrams and terms. Repetition, rhetorical questions, appeal to the reader are widely used to attract attention. A scientific text is usually characterized by an informative title, a description of the history of the subject, or an introduction to the topic. The distinctive features of a scientific text are characterized by emphasized logic, repetition with additional evidence, complex syntax, and professionally oriented topics.

Formal style is represented by various sub-styles or types: the language of working documents; language of legal documents; language of diplomacy; language of military documents. The main purpose of this type of communication is to determine the terms that bind the two parties and to reach a mutual agreement between the two contracting parties. Another characteristic of this style is the direct use of words in their meaning. It does not use a figurative meaning.

Studying texts in different functional styles, determining their parameters, selecting and using language tools in each of them, as well as linguistic and statistical research is not only necessary, but also one of the urgent tasks of language and its study.

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